

Effects of Use of CAPT, CWPT, and EM Instructional Approaches on Male and Female Students' Achievement in Civic Education

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Accepted: October 12th

Published: October 14th, 2022

Citations - APA

Nnabuike, E. K., & Agbo, C. N. (2022). Effects of Use of CAPT, CWPT, and EM Instructional Approaches on Male and Female Students' Achievement in Civic Education. *Global Journal of Education and Humanities*, 4(1), 18-28
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7199850>

This study examined the effects of the use of CAPT, CWPT, and EM instructional approaches on male and female students' achievement in civic education. The study adopted a quasi-experimental research design of pre-test, post-test, and, non-equivalent control group design among 240 students from size schools three boys and three girls) single-sex secondary schools in Agbani Education Zone of Enugu State. A purposive sampling technique was used in sampling the six schools to ensure that only the schools that have experienced Civic Education teachers were used for the study. Civic Education Achievement Test (CEAT) and civic Education Interest Scale (CEIS) were used in data collection. Data obtained from analyses of results on students' interest in Civic Education were analyzed using mean and standard deviation for the research questions and analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) for the hypothesis. The hypothesis was tested at a 0.05 level of significance. The result of the study revealed that both male and female students in CAPT, CWPT and EM groups recorded an increase in achievement. Male students recorded higher mean achievement scores than their female counterparts in the three groups (f-value of 1.309 and was not significant at 0.254). Based on the finding of the study, it was concluded that students taught Civic Education using the CAPT and CWPT had higher mean achievement scores than those taught with the conventional method. CAPT was, however, proven to be more effective than CWPT and expository methods as the CAPT students gained higher than their counterparts in the other groups.

ABSTRACT

Keywords: Cross Age Peers Tutoring (CAPT); Class Wide Peer Tutoring (CWPT); EM Instructional Approaches; Students Achievement; Civic Education

Introduction

Achievement refers to the instructional outcome normally in form of test/examination scores. It is a measure of students' success in an academic setting. Agbola and Onyemedede (2007) described academic achievement as the gain in knowledge of the students as a result of taking part in a learning program. Students' achievement depends on what teachers know about the subject they teach and their ability to use a variety of methods. The measurement of achievement is usually done using assignments, projects, tests, and examinations. Academic achievement is defined by Ossai (2004) as "the cognitive, affective and psychomotor domains attained by a student usually based on scores obtained".

Students' achievement is usually compared vis-à-vis the teaching method in education. They are also compared gender-wise. Gender refers to the biological orientation of a person based on sex (Garry, 2005). Agbo (2016) stated that in Nigeria's cultural setting, gender had strongly influenced sex roles, especially in the choice of school subject. Anibeze (2005) has a similar view when he found that girls excelled higher in verbal ability and boys excelled higher in visual-spatial ability. Achuonye (2004) discussing the effect of gender on the academic performance of students exposed to the problem-based learning showed that sex was not a determinant of academic performance irrespective of the pattern adopted. While some research findings support gender as a predictor of academic achievement, some fail to find any relationship between these variables.

Gender as a factor in peer tutoring and academic achievement has for some time generated a lot of concern for teachers. Peer tutoring has generated a great deal of scholarly interest in the field of education. It is viewed as an essential instructional strategy for inclusive education because it constitutes one of the strongholds of cooperative learning. It is regarded as an excellent resource for facilitating the mastery of interpersonal competencies. Fuchs, Fuchs, Mathes, and Martinez (2002) assert that socialization experiences that occur during peer tutoring can benefit both the tutor and the tutee by encouraging students to learn and increase their social standing among peers. Peer tutoring was found to be helpful in the socialization experience as the level of interaction among students both inside and outside the classroom improved significantly

Discussing gender and peer tutoring, Gevrielle (2008) held that the teaching method should facilitate the learning process for both genders. Teachers ought to be mindful that, unless the teaching method matches the different learning styles observed to be the dominant modality for each gender, students may not comprehend. Several researchers have divergent opinions on male and female academic performance despite varying teaching methods. Therefore, an investigation of gender influence as intended in this research work will throw more light on the issue. This present study was prompted by the quest to discover CAPT, CWPT, and EM Instructional Approaches to Male and Female Students' Achievement in Civic Education.

Statement of the Problem

The incessant fighting and quarreling among secondary school students and youths in general, social vices, cultism, thuggery, and disrespectfulness to constituted authorities even in the school may be a result of the conventional method of teaching civic education which is expository. This method has equally failed to enhance desirable academic achievement for the students over the years. Research evidence has confirmed students' persistent poor achievement at the junior level of education in Nigeria. Studies have attributed this ugly affair to poor and ineffective instructional strategy as the major cause. It was observed that most teachers still employ the traditional method of teaching instead of adopting the innovative strategy.

Therefore, there is a need to search for more proactive and effective instructional strategies such as peer tutoring, cross-age and class-wide types of cooperative-based learning that are likely to encourage and improve student discussions, and cross-fertilization of Civic Education ideas to enhance good academic achievement and interest. The teaching of civic education is geared towards the exposition of the child to various forms of cherished core values for their life roles as good citizens. Despite the lofty objective of Civic Education, it seems teachers in secondary school lack understanding of the efficacy of the subject in solving some Nigerian problems, because of the way and manner in which they teach the subject where the Civic Education teacher acts as an information giver or textbook guided classroom instructor is an attestation to this fact. It is therefore imperative to examine the influence of CAPT, CWPT, and EM Instructional Approaches on Male and Female Students' Achievement in Civic Education.

Review of Related Literature

Gender and Academic Achievement

Some studies have investigated the influence of gender on the interests and achievements of students. For instance, Ifeakor (2016) evaluated the influence of gender on students' academic achievement and interest in Biology using a commercially produced computer-assisted instruction package. Six research questions were posed and six hypotheses were formulated and tested at a 0.05 level of significance. The non-randomized control group design involving four intact classes was used. The sample for the study consisted of 140 senior secondary one (SSI) Biology students from two private secondary schools. Two instruments for data collection namely Biology Achievement Test (BAT) and Biology Interest Inventory (BII) were developed and validated. Internal consistency for BAT was computed at 0.89 using the Kuder Richardson formula (KR-20) and that of BII was 0.94 using Cronbach alpha. The data obtained were analyzed using mean, and standard deviation to answer the research questions and analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) for testing the hypotheses. The result of the analysis indicated that gender was a significant factor in the students' overall cognitive achievement in Biology. In the present study, the influence of gender on students' interest and achievement in civic education when exposed to cross-age and class-wide peer tutoring was investigated. Mean, standard deviation, and ANCOVA were used in data analysis as done in the reported study.

Asuquo and Onasanya (2016) examined gender differences in computer technology achievement. The setting was Graphcom Independent Educational Computer Laboratory, Ilorin. The participants were randomly selected junior secondary school (JSS) III students in Ilorin West Local Government Area of Kwara State for holiday computer technology instruction. A total of 30 students (15 boys and 15 girls) aged 15 and 16 years participated in this study. Scores from a pretest and posttest of male and female students were compared using paired sample t-tests with repeated measures and gender as the factor. Analysis of data showed gender differences in computer technology achievement. The findings were statistically significant. The study at hand examined gender on students' interest and achievement in civic education, and the setting will be in the southeastern part of the country. It is expected that the outcome of this study will add to the existing knowledge of students' interest and achievement in civic education.

Busola (2013) studied gender differences in students' achievement in secondary school Chemistry. It was a cross-sectional descriptive survey employing correlational methods to investigate gender differences in both boys and girls. The study comprised twelve (12) stratified selected public secondary schools in the Kakamega district. A total of 38 students responded to a five-item Chemistry Achievement Test (CAT) comprising descriptive mathematical and spatial ability items. The students also responded to the attitude scale and the teachers responded to the Chemistry teacher's questionnaire. The validity of the instrument was enhanced by a pilot study and the adoption of some already validation items. Quantitative data obtained from the CAT were analyzed using percentage mean, Pearson r, standard deviation, t-test, and ANOVA. The analysis indicated that males performed better than females in the Chemistry achievement test. It was recommended that in-service training would be useful to reduce gender differences in students' achievement in Chemistry. In the present study, the effects of gender on students' achievement and interest in civic education when exposed to cross-age and class-wide peer tutoring were investigated. Like the reported study, the present study used mean, standard deviation, and analysis of covariance on data analysis.

Oludipe (2012) investigated the influence of gender on Junior Secondary students' academic achievement in basic science using a cooperative learning teaching strategy. A total number of one hundred and twenty (120) students obtained from the intact classes of the three selected Junior Secondary Schools in the three selected Local Government Areas of Ogun State, South-west Nigeria, participated in the study. This study employed a quasi-experimental design. Lesson notes based on the jigsaw II cooperative learning strategy and Achievement Test for Basic Science Students (ATBSS) were the instruments used to collect the relevant data. The data collected was analyzed using descriptive and independent samples t-test statistical methods. The findings of this study revealed that there was no significant difference in the academic achievement of male and female students at the pretest, posttest, and delayed posttest levels respectively. This study is similar to the reported study because a quasi-experimental design was the design for both studies also the study investigated the influence of gender on Nigerian students at the basic level of education. However, the present study is on cross-age and class-wide peer tutoring.

Research Method

The study adopted a quasi-experimental research design of pre-test post-test, and non-equivalent control group design. The reason for this choice of design according to Danjuma (2015) is that quasi-experimental designs provide a substantial amount of control factors jeopardizing the validity of the research.

The pretest data were used to find out whether the subjects in the different groups are homogeneous or not. The experimental groups were termed group E, while the control group C. The non-randomized control group design will be represented diagrammatically thus:

Treatment Groups	Pretest	Experimental Treatment	Posttest
E-1	O	X ₁	O ₁
R E-2 →	O	X ₂	O ₁
C ↘	O	X ₀	O ₁

Where;

R = Random Assignment of Intact Classes to Treatment Groups

E1, 2 = Experimental Groups

C = Control Groups

X₁ = Cross-age Peer Tutoring

X₂ = Class-wide Peer Tutoring

X₀ = Expository method

O = Pre-test

O₁ = Post-test

Area of the Study

The study was carried out in Enugu State. Enugu State is one of the states that make up the South East geopolitical zone of the Federal Republic of Nigeria. Enugu State is made up of seventeen (17) Local Government Areas distributed into six (6) education zones namely: Agbani, Awgu, Enugu, Nsukka, Obollo-Afo, and Udi education zone. The choice for Enugu State (Agbani Education Zone) is because the Zone consists of predominantly interior, none motorable, and swamp areas where teachers that are not residents in her communities find it difficult to accept postings.

Population for the Study

The target populations for the study were all the Upper Basic II Civic Education students. The accessible population was the students in one stream, each from the six schools selected for the study. The total number of students that were used for the study was 4253 Upper Basic II students who were deemed appropriate as research subjects in the study. Their classes being non-certificate examination classes were available for the experiment. The students have been exposed to the basic Civic Education terms necessary for understanding the topics within the scope of this research.

Sample and Sampling Techniques

The sample for the study is 240 students from six secondary schools of (three boys and three girls) single-sex secondary schools in Agbani Education Zone of Enugu State. A purposive sampling technique was used in sampling the six schools to ensure that only the schools that have experienced Civic Education teachers were used for the study. Each of the sampled schools has between 4-10 streams of Upper Basic II classes, while one intact class was chosen using simple random sampling. Thus, there is a total of six (6) intact classes chosen for the study. The number of students in a class varied from 30-50. These intact classes were randomly assigned to experimental and control groups through balloting. All the subjects in each of the sample intact classes that were used for the study were 240 (two hundred and forty) in number. This comprises 157 subjects for the experimental groups of cross-age and class-wide (two boys and two girls single-sex secondary schools) and 83 subjects for expository methods (one boy and one girl's single-sex secondary schools).

An instrument for Data Collection

Two instruments were developed by the researcher for data collection. The instruments are

- I. Civic Education Achievement Test (CEAT) and
- II. Civic Education Interest Scale (CEIS)

Civic Education Achievement Test

The instrument that was used for data collection is termed Civic Education Achievement Test (CEAT). This instrument was developed by the researcher. CEAT consists of 50-item multiple-choice objective questions. Each item has four response options labeled A-D with one correct answer and three distractors. The instrument is designed to explore the cognitive, affective, and psychomotor skills of learners in Civic Education. The content is drawn from the following topics: National values, integrity, contentment, discipline, respect for rules and regulations, courage, talents and skills, and citizenship. 50-item-item achievement test (CEAT) is designed to measure the student's achievement in Civic Education. The same sets of test items were used for the pretest and posttest

Civic Education Interest Scale

This instrument contains 25 items designed to determine students' interest in Civic Education. The students' interest in Civic Education will be rated using a four-point rating scale. The options are: strongly agree (SA), agree (A), disagree (D), and strongly disagree (SD). The students were required to express their interest in Civic Education by ticking in a most appropriate column against the items stated. The scores that were obtained by the students on the scale will indicate the level of students' interest towards civic education. The scores were used in determining the mean interest score towards Civic Education by the group

Validation of the Instrument

To establish the validity of the instruments, the two instruments were given to one expert in measurement and evaluation, one in curriculum and instruction, all from Enugu State University of Science and Technology (ESUT), and another in Civic Education from Union Secondary School, Awkunanaw Enugu. The valid comments and corrections were used by the researcher in making the final copies of the CEAT and CEIS. The final copies were certified to have both face and content validity for data collection

Reliability of the Instrument

The reliability of CEAT was determined using Kuder-Richardson's formula 20, because it is most suitable in multiple-choice items with right or wrong answers, and very appropriate in determining the internal consistency of items scored dichotomously (Ezechi, 2004). The reliability of CEAT was established through trial-testing of the instrument on 50 Upper Basic II students (25 males and 25 females) drawn randomly from two single-sex secondary schools (Ezza Boys and Girls Special Science School, Ezilo) in Ebonyi State. The researcher employed the Kuder-Richardson formula 20 (K-R20) to compute the reliability coefficient of CEAT. The 50 copies of the instrument were administered to the 50 students randomly chosen for the trial testing. To obtain the individual scores the tests were scored using mean score and standard deviation, the variance (S^2), and the proportion of those who scored the items wrongly was worked out. The reliability of the CEAT using K-R (20) was 0.82

Reliability of Students' Interest in Civic Education

To determine the internal consistency or reliability of the interest scale, forty (40) copies of the instrument were trial tested on a sample of 40 Upper Basic II students in two single-sex secondary schools, one male and one female in Ebonyi State. This State was not part of the study area. Cronbach Alpha (α) was used in determining the reliability coefficient which was found to be 0.80

Experimental Procedure

The experimental procedure was as follows:

Six intact classes were used and randomly assigned to treatment and control groups. The experimental groups (two male and two female single-sex schools) were taught Civic Education with CAPT and CWPT peer tutoring strategies, while the control groups (one male and one female single-sex school) with the expository method.

Experimental group, I cross-age peer tutoring (CAPT)

- I. The selections of cross-age student tutors were based on their academic achievements. This is because older students with relatively advanced skills were grouped with younger students who were

deficient in some skill areas to deliver instruction. In this research, SSI students tutored a group of 5-8 students of Upper Basic II as tutees.

- II. Their old results and admission documents ascertain their level of intelligence and age.
- III. Assigning of students: SSI student tutors who were more knowledgeable were assigned to their cross-age groups of upper basic II students to tutor.
- IV. The student tutors tutored based on the instruction of the prepared lesson plan by the Civic Education teacher who supervised the lesson.

Experimental group II class-wide peer tutoring (CWPT)

- I. The teacher presented a mini-lesson of about thirty (30) minutes to acquaint the students with the knowledge as the more brilliant were paired with special consideration for students with academic problems within the same class.
- II. The teacher allows them to have 10 – 15 minutes of discussion among themselves about what was taught. Hence, the brilliant students paired with the less brilliant helped them to understand the lesson better.
- III. General class interaction: Here the Civic Education teacher asked questions, conducted discussions, and evaluated the lesson.

Control Group: Expository Teaching

Set Induction: the class teacher began by arousing the interest of the students.

Instructional procedure: the teacher began the lesson using an explanation, use of examples, questioning skills, instructional materials, student-teacher interaction, evaluation, and closure.

The civic education teacher and the peer tutors that were used for the study were briefed by the researcher for one week before the commencement of the study. The treatment commenced after the administration of the pre-CEAT to ascertain the level of achievement of students before the treatment was administered by the civic teachers. The pre-CEAT was administered on the first day of the experiment. The pre-CEAT items were taken away from the students after administration. After the pretests, the students were taught topics in Civic Education for six weeks using the researcher's prepared lesson plan and sample.

The peer tutors that were used for the study made use of the necessary civic education materials for teaching the concept in the Upper Basic school. They used the Civic Education lesson plans for the content prepared by the researcher as a guide through interaction. The researcher ensured that:

The lessons were well taught following the peer tutoring procedures:

Tutoring session: putting peer tutoring into practice requires proper planning. Some factors that need consideration include When, where, length, and frequency of each session. As a civic education teacher, there is a need to decide how many students to be involved initially and eventually in peer tutoring.

The following steps were followed:

- I. The class teachers arranged the students into groups known as teams in the cross-age peer tutoring and paired the students in the class-wide peer tutoring groups in the schools involved.
- II. The teacher assigned each team a different mini-topic, each team worked differently, and this was used to control the interaction effect.
- III. The teacher instructed the tutors to teach the topics they prepared to their team members
- IV. The teacher instructed all the tutors who prepared on the same mini-topic from various teams to come together and form "expert groups for mini-topics". These groups then discussed and refined their understanding of the mini-topic.

Method of Data Collection

The Civic Education Achievement Test (CEAT) and Civic Education Interest Scale (CEIS) were used for data collection. They were administered to the subjects in their classes before the treatment as the pretest. The scripts were marked and scores were kept.

At the end of the treatment, the pretest was rearranged so that the students did not identify it and it was administered as a posttest. Two weeks after the post-test, the items in the instrument for interest were administered and used as an interesting test to test the interest of students in civic education. The pre-test, post-test, and interest tests were administered by the research assistants (class teachers) who experimented.

Method of Data Analysis

Data obtained from analyses of results students' interest in Civic Education were analyzed using mean and standard deviation for the research questions and analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) for the hypothesis. The hypothesis was tested at a 0.05 level of significance.

Result Presentation

Table 1: Mean Achievement Scores and Standard Deviations of Male and Female Students Taught Civic Education Using Cross-Age Peer Tutoring (CAPT), Class Wide Peer Tutoring (CWPT), and Expository Method (EM)

Groups	Gender	Number	Pre-test		Post-test	
			Mean (\bar{x})	Standard Deviation (s)	Mean (\bar{x})	Standard Deviation (s)
CAPT	Male	36	43.50	10.41	77.53	11.40
	Female	40	40.80	10.86	76.40	11.19
CWPT	Male	42	40.45	11.75	68.36	10.89
	Female	39	39.74	11.29	64.64	12.66
Expository	Male	40	41.55	11.68	51.37	14.26
	Female	43	38.58	10.61	49.02	11.55

Table 1 above showed the results of mean achievement scores and standard deviations of male and female students taught Civic Education using Cross-Age Peer Tutoring (CAPT), Class Wide Peer Tutoring (CWPT), and Expository Method (EM) in both Pretest and Posttest. The results show that the mean pretest achievement score and standard deviation of male students taught with CAPT were 43.50 and 10.41 respectively, while the post-test mean achievement score and standard deviation were 77.53 and 11.40 respectively. For the female students taught with CAPT, the mean achievement score and standard deviation at the pretest were 40.80 and 10.86 respectively; at the post-test, they recorded mean achievement and standard deviation of 76.40 and 11.19 respectively.

For the CWPT group, the pre-test means achievement score and standard deviation of the male students at the pretest were 40.45 and 11.75 respectively, while the post-test mean achievement score and standard deviation were 68.36 and 10.89 respectively. For the female students, the mean achievement score and standard deviation at the pretest were 39.74 and 11.29 respectively; while on the post-test, they recorded 64.64 and 12.66 respectively.

On the other hand, for the expository group, the pre-test means achievement score and standard deviation of the male students at the pretest were 41.55 and 11.68 respectively, while the post-test mean achievement score and standard deviation were 51.37 and 14.26 respectively. For the female students, the mean achievement score and standard deviation at the pretest were 38.58 and 10.61 respectively; while on the post-test, they recorded 49.02 and 11.55 respectively.

The results of this analysis are that both male and female students in all the groups recorded high post-test achievement scores. In other words, both male and female students in the two groups recorded higher mean scores in the post-test than in the pretest. However, male students recorded higher achievement scores than their female counterparts in both the pretest and posttest, in the three groups. High extreme scores were observed for the male students in the expository group as indicated by the high standard deviation (14.26). The least post-test achievement scores were also recorded among male and female students in the expository group.

Test of Hypothesis

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught civic education using CAPT, CWPT, and EM as measured by the Civic Education Achievement Test (CEAT).

Table 2: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) on the Mean Achievement Scores of Male and Female Students Taught Civic Education Using Cross-Age Peer Tutoring (CAPT), Class Wide Peer Tutoring (CWPT), and Expository Method (EM)

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
Corrected Model	347.379 ^a	1	347.379	1.309	.254	NS
Intercept	988766.462	1	988766.462	3727.219	.000	
GENDER	347.379	1	347.379	1.309	.254	
Error	63137.271	238	265.283			
Total	1051908.000	240				
Corrected Total	63484.650	238				

Table 2 showed the Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) on the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught civic education with CAPT, CWPT, and EM as measured by the Civic Education Achievement Test (CEAT). In the table, gender as the main effect gave an f-value of 1.309 and was not significant at 0.254. Since 0.254 is not less than 0.05, it means that at a 0.05 significant level, the f-value is not significant. Hence, hypothesis 2 was accepted as stated. The study, therefore, concluded that there was no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught civic education with CAPT, CWPT, and EM.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the post-test mean interest scores of male and female students taught civic education using CAPT, CWPT, and EM as measured by the Civic Education Interest Scale (CEIS)

Table 3: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) on the Post-Test Mean Interest Scores of Male and Female Students Taught Civic Education Using Cross-Age Peer Tutoring (CAPT), Class Wide Peer Tutoring (CWPT), and Expository Method (EM)

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
Corrected Model	.214 ^a	1	.214	.653	.420	NS
Intercept	1791.417	1	1791.417	5474.891	.000	
GENDER	.214	1	.214	.653	.420	
Error	77.875	238	.327			
Total	1869.352	240				
Corrected Total	78.089	238				

Table 3 showed the Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) on the mean interest scores of male and female students taught Civic Education with CAPT, CWPT, and EM as measured by the Civic Education Achievement Test (CEAT). In the table, gender as the main effect gave an f-value of 0.653 and was not significant at 0.420. Since 0.420 is not less than 0.05, it means that at a 0.05 significant level, the f-value is not significant. Hence, hypothesis 4 was accepted as stated. The study, therefore, concluded that there was no significant difference between the mean interest scores of male and female students taught Civic Education with CAPT, CWPT, and EM.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant interaction between mode of instruction and gender on students' achievement in Civic Education

Table 4: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) on the Interaction between Mode of Instruction and Gender on Students' Achievement in Civic Education

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
Corrected Model	29038.040 ^a	2	14519.020	99.894	.000	S
Intercept	277662.188	1	277662.188	1910.375	.000	
METHOD * GENDER	29038.040	2	14519.020	99.894	.000	
Error	34446.610	237	145.344			
Total	1051908.000	240				
Corrected Total	63484.650	238				

Table 4 showed the interaction effect between mode of instruction and gender on students' achievement in Civic Education. The results indicated that the main interaction effect gave an f-value of 99.894. This was significant at 0.000. Since 0.000 was less than 0.05, this meant that at 0.05 level, the f-value of 99.894 was significant. This implied that the interactive effect of mode of instruction and gender on students' mean achievement was statistically significant. The study, therefore, concluded that there was a significant interaction between the mode of instruction and gender on students' achievement in Civic Education.

Discussion of Findings

The results revealed that both male and female students in CAPT, CWPT, and EM groups recorded an increase in achievement. Male students recorded higher mean achievement scores than their female counterparts in the three groups. Further analysis revealed that there was, however, no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students in all the groups. This is consistent with the finding of Agbola, and Onyemedede, (2007) that there was no significant difference in gender achievement between cooperative and control groups, but male students had a slightly higher mean score than female students. Gevrielle (2008) equally observed that teaching methods should facilitate the learning process for both genders. The finding is also in agreement with the submission of Oludipe (2012) that there was no significant difference in the academic achievement of male and female students at the pretest, posttest, and delayed posttest levels respectively. Similarly, the finding corroborates the report of Achuonye (2004), which, discussing the effect of gender on the academic performance of students exposed to the problem – based learning, showed that sex was not a determinant of academic performance irrespective of the pattern adopted. Herbert and Stipeck (2013), on the emergence of gender differences in children's perception of their academic competence, found no gender difference in achievement. The finding is in agreement with the work carried out by Babalola and Fayombo (2009) and Richman (2014) where they found that there was no statistically significant difference in students' achievements based on gender. The result implies that students' gender has no effect on their achievement when they are taught using CAPT and CWPT.

The finding is, however, inconsistent with findings by Ibiri (2012) and Godpower-Echie and Amadi (2013) who indicated that there is a positive correlation between gender and students' achievement. Similarly, Naderi, Abdulah, Hamid, and Sharir (2008) found a significant difference between the achievement of males and females. The finding further contradicts the submission of Oludipe and Awokoya (2010) that female students perform better with class-wide peer tutoring. Given the finding that male and female students recorded no significant difference in achievement, CAPT and CWPT are considered to be effective in teaching Civic Education in such a manner as to ensure positive learning across gender.

Conclusion

The findings of this study revealed, among others, that students taught Civic Education using the CAPT and CWPT had higher mean achievement scores than those taught with the conventional method. CAPT was, however, proven to be more effective than CWPT and expository methods as the CAPT students gained higher than their counterparts in the other groups. It was also found that male students slightly recorded higher achievement than their female counterparts in all the groups. Given that the differences in achievement and interest were not significant with regard to gender, it indicates that both male and female students learned better using CAPT and CWPT. This is an indication that Cooperative Learning Strategies, especially CAPT are effective for teaching and learning of Civic Education in secondary schools, and should therefore be promoted in order to boost students' achievement and interest in the subject.

Recommendations

Based on the above implications and findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

- I. The result of this study showed that the students taught Civic Education with CAPT and CWPT recorded higher mean achievement score than those taught with EM. Hence, the serving Civic Education teachers of Secondary Schools should adopt the use of well-structured peer tutoring in Civic Education lessons.

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